

pH dependent speciation and removal of chromium from environmental samples using a chelating resin containing derivatised L-methionine

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Abstract : pH dependent chemical speciation of inorganic chromium species and their removal from environmental samples have been performed on a chelating resin having *N*-(3-indolylmethyl) L-methionine moiety. The novelty of the resin is that it can bind both Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} at two different pH. The maximum sorption capacity of the resin for Cr^{III} is 1.37 mmol g⁻¹ at pH 8.6 where no sorption of Cr^{VI} was observed. Again, maximum sorption of Cr^{VI} is 1.752 mmol g⁻¹ at pH 4.0 where sorption of Cr^{III} is almost nil. We have observed complete desorption of Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} with 3.0 mol L⁻¹ HCl and 4.0 mol L⁻¹ HCl respectively. Detection limits (three times of the standard deviation for blank) for Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} has been found as 0.4 mg mL⁻¹ and 1.3 mg mL⁻¹ respectively. Sorption of both Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} has been found to follow a second order rate law. The developed method has been used for the chemical speciation and removal of chromium from different environmental samples and validated by standard/reference method. The concentration of chromium has been measured by flame atomic absorption spectrometer (FAAS).

Keywords : Chromium, speciation, chelating resin, L-methionine, FAAS.

Introduction

Rapidly growing interest in the chemical speciation of trace metals dispersed in our environment is mainly due to their different physiological, biological and chemical functions. Toxicity of metal ions depend on their oxidation states e.g. Cr^{VI} compounds are carcinogenic¹ whereas Cr^{III} is considered to be an essential nutrient for the maintenance of normal glucose tolerance factor². That is why speciation of chromium in environmental samples is very crucial and a long standing analytical challenge. The major sources of chromium toxicity is due to the steel factories, tanning industries, electroplating industries, dying industries, leaching from sanitary land fills and cooling water towers where Cr^{VI} is used as a corrosion inhibitor. Chemical and pharmaceutical industries use chromium compounds as catalyst³. Very few instrumental techniques, for example, electro-analytical techniques can directly determine Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} in real samples. Hence, different researchers have used solvent extraction⁴, co-precipi-

tation^{5,6} and solid-phase extraction (SPE)⁷⁻¹⁰ for separation and pre-concentration of the different chromium species before measurement. Amongst these, SPE has more advantages as the sorbent can be reused for many cycles (economic), easy to handle and reasonably fast process. Least availability of costly and sophisticated instruments like ICP-MS or ICP-AES in many laboratories have forced us to use atomic absorption spectrometry (AAS) for measurement of chromium concentration. US EPA has set the threshold value for total Cr as 0.1 mg L⁻¹ in drinking water whereas WHO has prescribed the tolerance level¹¹ for Cr^{VI} as 50 µg L⁻¹. Reports on pH dependent sorption of Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} by chelating resins are few^{9,10,12-15}. For last couple of years we are working on the synthesis and applications of different derivatized amino acids, particularly of L-methionine¹⁶⁻¹⁸. In this report, we thoroughly discuss the pH dependent speciation and removal of chromium from environmental samples using a chelating resin containing *N*-(3-indolylmethyl) L-methionine.

Experimental

Reagents and solutions :

All chemicals were analytical reagent (A.R.) grade. All solutions were prepared in double distilled (d.d.) water. Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} stock solutions (1000 mg L⁻¹) were prepared using Cr(NO₃)₃·9H₂O (Merck) and K₂CrO₄ (Merck) in 0.5 mol L⁻¹ HNO₃ and d.d. water respectively. The solutions were standardized against standard solutions of Cr^{III} (1000 mg L⁻¹) supplied by SOLUTIONS plus inc. (Missouri, USA) which was tested vs NIST SRM # 3108a using AAS. Working solutions (50 mg L⁻¹) were obtained by diluting respective stock solutions with d.d. water generated from Milli-Q Millipore® (18.2 MΩ cm⁻¹ conductivity) purification system (Bedford, MA, USA). The solutions of other metal ions were prepared from A.R. grade reagents. pH of the solutions were adjusted using buffer solutions¹³ viz. HCl-KCl buffer (pH 1 and 2), citrate buffer (pH 3, 4, 5 and 6), phosphate buffer (pH 7 and 8), boric acid-borax buffer (pH 8 and 9), glycine-NaOH buffer (pH 10).

Instrumentation and apparatus :

A VARIAN (Spectra AA 55) flame atomic absorption spectrophotometer (Australia) was used. All measurements were performed using integrated absorbance (peak area). Hollow cathode lamp for Cr was operated at 7.0 mA at wave length 357.9 nm and at slit width 0.2 nm. Air and acetylene have flow rates 3.5 and 1.5 L min⁻¹ respectively. IR spectra were recorded on a JASCO FTIR spectrophotometer (model : FTIR-H20). Thermogravimetric analysis was done on a Perkin-Elmer TG/DTA lab system 1 (Technology by SII). pH measurements were performed with Systronics digital pH meter (model : 335). UV-Vis spectra were obtained from a Shimadzu spectrophotometer (model : UV2101PC). A Kratos MALDI-TOF 1 mass spectrometer using the matrix α-ACHC and an extraction voltage of 4 kV was used for mass spectrometry. ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded on a 200 MHz and 50 MHz Varian Gemini 200 and optical rotations were determined on a Perkin-Elmer model 341 polarimeter at 589 nm. Glass apparatus were soaked with 4 mol L⁻¹ HNO₃ overnight and cleaned with double distilled water. A short glass column with an inner diameter of 10 mm and a length of 100 mm, equipped with porous frits, was filled up to a height of 30 mm with a suspension of 1 g of the chelating resin in d.d. water.

Sampling¹⁹ :

Waste water samples from different sources like tannery industrial water at Kolkata, industrial waste water at Durgapur, West Bengal, India, were collected in well cleaned polyethylene bottles. pH of the real samples were noted using a pen pH meter. Then the samples were acidified with 0.05 mol L⁻¹ H₂SO₄ to resist any unwanted precipitation of the metal hydroxide. The samples were filtered through a 0.45 μm Milipore membrane filter.

Preparation of the resin :

The resin has been synthesized using a reported method²⁰.

Stability of the resin :

250 mg of resin was shaken with 100 mL of acid or alkaline solutions of different ionic strengths for 7 days. Then filtered and washed with deionised water to free from acid or alkali and dried under vacuum. The metal ion exchange capacity was measured. Thermal stability of the resin has been studied by thermogravimetry.

Water regain :

Air dried resin in basic form was stirred in double distilled water for 48 h, then filtered off by suction, weighed, dried at 100 °C for 48 h and reweighed.

Hydrogen ion capacity :

1.0 g resin was first converted into its acidic form by treating with 6 mol L⁻¹ HCl. The resin was first filtered off, washed with water and then dried at 100 °C for 6 h to remove free HCl. The acidic hydrogen content of the resin was then determined by back titration with a standard alkali solution. The acidic form of the resin was equilibrated with 20 mL of 0.1 mol L⁻¹ sodium hydroxide solution for 6 h at room temperature under stirring condition. Then the solution was filtered under suction, washed with de-ionized water and the excess alkali was titrated with standard solution of 0.1 mol L⁻¹ HCl.

Chromium ion uptake as a function of pH :

A batch technique was used, taking metal ion in excess to the resin. Capacities were determined in the pH range 1.0–10.0. To a glass stoppered centrifuge tube (diameter 2.0 cm) containing 40 mg of the dry resin in basic form, 10 mL of the desired pH solution was added. After equilibration of this mixture 30 ml of 50 μg mL⁻¹ metal ion solution was added and the mixture was shaken for

24 h. The pH of the equilibrating solution was adjusted by appropriate buffer solution. After 24 h, the solutions were filtered under suction, washed with de-ionized water to remove adhering metal ions. To confirm that the resin absorbs chromium species, FTIR spectra of the Cr^{III} loaded resin was recorded in Fig. 5. Then the adsorbed metal ion is eluted with suitable eluting agent. The concentration of the eluted metal ions is measured by flame AAS using air-acetylene flame.

Desorption of metal ions :

Resin thus obtained after uptake of chromium ion in the above mentioned batch technique was shaken with 25 mL of different eluants (1.0 mol L⁻¹ to 6.0 mol L⁻¹ HNO₃ and 1.0 mol L⁻¹ to 6 mol L⁻¹ HCl) and filtered. The concentration of metal ion in the filtrate was determined by FAAS.

Kinetic studies :

The concentrations of Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} absorbed by the resin at the pH where maximum absorption takes place were monitored at different time intervals. From that data, different kinetic parameters such as rate constant etc. were determined for the sorption of Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} on the resin using batch technique.

Column preparation :

Air dried resin (1.0 g) was immersed in double distilled water and allowed to swell for 24 h. A glass column (100 mm × 10 mm) was packed with swollen beads to a bed volume of 2 ml. Before starting the experiment, the resin bed was thoroughly washed with 0.1 mol L⁻¹ HNO₃ followed by d.d. water till the effluent is free from acid. Sorption and desorption characteristics for Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} in the column were studied at the optimum flow rate. Any adhering metal ions (not adsorbed) were completely washed out by using solutions of appropriate pH. The sorbed Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} were completely eluted by 4 mol L⁻¹ HCl. Concentrations of each chromium species thus eluted was measured as described earlier. Adsorption capacities for the non-functionalized chloromethylated resin was measured at pH 8.6 and 4.0 to ascertain that it has no absorption for Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} respectively.

Effect of flow rate :

The sample flow rate has a significant effect not only on the retention of chromium species on to the sorbent, but also on their desorption by suitable eluting agents.

The sample flow rate was varied in the range 0.5–15 mL min⁻¹. The recovery of chromium species from the resin was monitored using FAAS.

Effect of sample volume :

Sample volume is one of the important analytical parameter to be studied to obtain the maximum pre-concentration factor. 50–2000 mL of sample solutions containing 50 µg of Cr^{VI} (as it has higher absorption over Cr^{III}) were passed through the column containing 250 mg resin under the optimum conditions. The concentration of Cr^{VI} in the effluent was monitored by FAAS.

Procedure for Cr^{VI} and Cr^{III} :

25 ml solution containing 50 µg mL⁻¹ chromium(VI), made in appropriate buffer (pH range from 1–10) was passed through 1 g of the resin, preconditioned at the requisite pH, at a flow rate of 5.0 mL min⁻¹. Then the column was thoroughly washed with d.d. water to remove adhering species followed by elution with 6.5 mL of 4.0 mol L⁻¹ HCl. The concentration of Cr^{VI} was measured in flame AAS. The similar procedure performed for Cr^{III} also and 5 mL of 3.0 mol L⁻¹ HCl can completely elute the sorbed Cr^{III} from the resin.

Applications :

The waste water samples from different sources (three samples from tannery industrial area, Kolkata and three samples from Durgapur Industrial belt, West Bengal, India) were filtered through a 0.45 µm Milipore membrane filter. pH of 250 mL of the filtrate was adjusted to 4.0 and fed onto preconditioned column maintained at the same pH. After elution with 10 ml of the eluent, the concentration of Cr^{VI} is measured by FAAS. Another 250 mL portion of filtered water was adjusted to pH 8.6 using buffer solution and fed onto preconditioned column maintained at the same pH. After elution with of the eluent, the concentration of Cr^{III} is measured by FAAS. Thus, we can also know the total chromium present in the sample. The results were compared to a reference method²¹.

Results and discussion

Synthesis and characterization of the resin :

Synthesis and characterization of the resin has already been reported²⁰. The time required for 50% uptake of the maximum capacity was found to be 18 min and 26 min for Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} species respectively.

Sorption and desorption of Cr species :

The hydrogen ion capacity of the resin was found to be 2.35 mmol g⁻¹. The sorption of Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} on the chelating resin as a function of pH is shown in Fig. 1. Maximum absorption capacity of the resin for Cr^{III} at pH 8.6 is 1.37 mmol g⁻¹ at which absorption of Cr^{VI} is

Fig. 1. Adsorption capacity of Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} as a function of pH.

almost nil whereas for Cr^{VI} at pH 4.0 is 1.752 mmol g⁻¹ while no absorption of Cr^{III} takes place at this pH. Thus it is possible to separate and estimate simultaneously Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} by mere adjustment of pH using the same resin. The effect of different eluents on desorption of Cr species is shown in Table 1. Both Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} were eluted completely by 3.0 and 4.0 mol L⁻¹ HCl respectively.

Table 1. Effect of different eluents on the desorption of Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} (N = 3)

Eluent	Recovery (%)	
	Cr ^{III}	Cr ^{VI}
1.0 mol L ⁻¹ HNO ₃	15 ± 2	19 ± 1
2.0 mol L ⁻¹ HNO ₃	23 ± 5	28 ± 4
3.0 mol L ⁻¹ HNO ₃	39 ± 4	34 ± 5
4.0 mol L ⁻¹ HNO ₃	59 ± 2	42 ± 2
5.0 mol L ⁻¹ HNO ₃	67 ± 3 ^a	78 ± 3 ^a
6.0 mol L ⁻¹ HNO ₃	71 ± 4 ^a	83 ± 4 ^a
1.0 mol L ⁻¹ HCl	58 ± 2 ^a	33 ± 5 ^a
2.0 mol L ⁻¹ HCl	71 ± 6 ^a	69 ± 5 ^a
3.0 mol L ⁻¹ HCl	101 ± 4 ^a	84 ± 3 ^a
4.0 mol L ⁻¹ HCl	100 ± 3 ^a	100 ± 2 ^a

^aProbably, the ligating group decomposes slightly, causing lower recovery.

Kinetic parameters :

The rate of exchange of metal ion by a chelating resin is controlled by a second order kinetic equation²². Using the equation $\ln Z = 2kQ_0(Q_0 - Q_\alpha)t/Q_\alpha$, where $Z = [Q_t(Q_0 - 2Q_\alpha) + Q_0 Q_\alpha] / Q_0(Q_\alpha - Q_t)$ developed by Turse and Riemen²³. The rate constant k is calculated from the slope S from the equation : $S = 2k Q_0 (Q_0 - Q_\alpha) / Q_\alpha$, where Q_t is the amount (mmol) of metal ion exchanged at time t , Q_α is the maximum exchange capacity (mmol) at equilibrium and Q_0 is the amount (mmol) of chelating resin, in terms of millimoles of Na⁺ exchanged after 24 h. A plot of $\ln Z$ versus t is linear and passing through zero. Fig. 2 has provided the values for slope (s) and rate constant (k) for Cr^{VI} sorption as 0.0323 and 4.02×10^{-5} respectively whereas Fig. 3 has provided the values for slope (s) and rate constant (k) for Cr^{III} sorption as 0.00678 and 9.41×10^{-5} respectively.

Fig. 2. Second order plot for the sorption of Cr^{VI} on the resin.

Binding of Cr species to the resin :

FTIR spectra of the IM resin and Cr loaded IM resins are shown in Figs. 4 and 5 respectively. The blue shift in the wave number of characteristic chelating functional group indicates the binding of the Cr species on to the resin.

Influence of flow rate of sample :

Effect of sample flow rate on the sorption-desorption processes on to the resin is shown in Fig. 6 which indicates that the optimum flow rate should be 5 mL min⁻¹.

Fig. 3. Second order plot for the sorption of Cr^{III} on the resin.

Effect of diverse ions :

In column operation, the presence of macro amounts (200 folds) of alkali, alkaline earth and transition metal ions were investigated. Only Cu^{II} and Fe^{III} did interfere to some extent. However, prior addition of thiocyanate ion could efficiently mask them. Interferences from different anions were also recorded. For this study, binary mixtures containing 2 µg mL⁻¹ Cr^{III} or Cr^{VI} solution were mixed with other ions having concentration 400 µg mL⁻¹. The results have been summarized in Table 2.

Effect of amount of resin :

From Fig. 8, it can be concluded that after 60 mg of the resin, recoveries for Cr species remain constant (100%). So, 60 mg resin was chosen for all work.

Fig. 4. FTIR spectrum of the resin (IM).

Effect of sample volume/breakthrough volume :

It was observed from the Fig. 7 that the percent sorption drops with the sample volume after 1100 mL for Cr^{III} and 1600 mL for Cr^{VI}. The highest pre-concentration factors achieved for Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} are 1100/5 = 220 and 1600/6.5 = 246 respectively, when the final volume of the eluent were 5.0 and 6.5 mL of 3.0 mol L⁻¹ and 4.0 mol L⁻¹ HCl respectively.

Effect of temperature :

It has been found that sorption capacity of the resin increases with increasing temperature to a maximum value at 50 °C (Fig. 9).

Effect of time :

From Fig. 10, it is obvious that at optimum conditions sorption of Cr species on the resin increases with time and reaches to a maximum value at ~40 min with no further change.

Fig. 5. FTIR spectrum of the Cr^{III} loaded resin.

Fig. 6. Influence of sample flow rate on the sorption of Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI}.

Fig. 7. Sample breakthrough volume graph for sorption of Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI}.

Elution volume and elution flow rate :

It has been found that 5.0 mL of 3.0 mol L⁻¹ HNO₃ and 6.5 mL of 4.0 mol L⁻¹ HNO₃ could completely elute sorbed Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} respectively (Fig. 11). It was also found that both Cr species could be recovered quantitatively (above 98%) with eluent flow rate of 0.5–1.5 mL min⁻¹. Consequently, 1.0 mL min⁻¹ elution flow rate was selected for the entire studies.

Evaluation of method performance :

Calibration curve for quantitative analysis was linear up to 8 µg ml⁻¹ with a regression coefficient (*R*²) of 0.997. Detection limits (3σ of the blank signal; *N* = 20) for Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} were 0.40 mg mL⁻¹ and 1.30 mg mL⁻¹ respectively. Precision of the method was evaluated by successive retention and elution cycle. Recovery was 97.4 ± 2.6% at 98% confidence level.

Fig. 8. Effect of mass of resin on sorption of Cr species.

Table 2. Effect of diverse ions on the sorption of Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} onto resin

Foreign ion ^a	Recovery (%)	
	Cr ^{III}	Cr ^{VI}
Al ^{III}	97.2	-
Fe ^{III}	93.1	-
Cu ^{II}	94.3	-
Hg ^{II}	95.5	-
Ag ^I	94.8	-
Cd ^{II}	92.6	-
Pb ^{II}	85.3	-
Li ^I	95.9	-
Zn ^{II}	93.6	-
Mn ^{II}	95.0	-
Mg ^{II}	98.25	-
Ca ^{II}	97.95	-
Na ^I	99.35	-
PO ₄ ³⁻	-	88.7
VO ₃ ⁻	-	92.0
AsO ₄ ³⁻	-	97.5
MoO ₄ ²⁻	-	98.3

^aIn each case the amount of foreign ion was added 200 fold excess with respect to Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI}.

Applications :

Separation of Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} from binary synthetic mixtures :

Different amounts of Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} were mixed in different sets (each set in duplicate) with a total volume of 100 mL. In one set, pH was adjusted to 4.0 (for Cr^{VI} sorption only) and in the other, pH was adjusted to 8.6

Fig. 9. Effect of temperature on sorption of both Cr species

Fig. 10. Adsorption capacity vs time (min).

Fig. 11. Recovery of Cr species as a function of eluent volume.

Table 3. Separation of Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} in binary synthetic mixtures

No. of observations	Amount taken (µg)	Amount found (µg)	Error (%)
1	Cr ^{III} -50	Cr ^{III} -50.26 ± 0.02	0.03
	Cr ^{VI} -50	Cr ^{VI} -50.08 ± 0.01	1.92
2	Cr ^{III} -50	Cr ^{III} -48.5 ± 0.03	1.50
	Cr ^{VI} -30	Cr ^{VI} -32.6 ± 0.2	2.60
3	Cr ^{III} -20	Cr ^{III} -21.2 ± 0.01	1.20
	Cr ^{VI} -70	Cr ^{VI} -69.5 ± 0.03	0.05
4	Cr ^{III} -20	Cr ^{III} -22.01 ± 0.02	2.01
	Cr ^{VI} -30	Cr ^{VI} -29.6 ± 0.01	0.40
5	Cr ^{III} -70	Cr ^{III} -30.4 ± 0.4	0.40
	Cr ^{VI} -30	Cr ^{VI} -29.1 ± 0.5	0.90

Table 4. Level of chromium species in environmental samples as determined by application of the present method (N = 4)

Sample no.	Present method (µg ml ⁻¹)		Reference method ²⁴ (µg ml ⁻¹)	
	Cr ^{III}	Cr ^{VI}	Cr ^{III}	Cr ^{VI}
1 ^a	681.2 ± 0.2	595 ± 2	684.2 ± 1	598 ± 3
2 ^a	575 ± 3	512 ± 4	570 ± 4	509 ± 5
3 ^a	467 ± 1	411 ± 3	472 ± 3	415 ± 2
4 ^b	65.3 ± 3	54.3 ± 1	62.3 ± 3	51.3 ± 1
5 ^b	43.1 ± 3	41.2 ± 4	41.1 ± 2	43.2 ± 4
6 ^b	35.5 ± 4	37.5 ± 5	33.5 ± 0.8	36.0 ± 5

^aTannery water. ^bIndustrial water.

(for Cr^{III} sorption only). They were passed through the resin. After elution, the concentration of Cr was measured using FAAS. The results have been summarized in Table 3.

Real samples analysis :

Waste water samples from tannery industrial area, Kolkata and Durgapur Industrial belt, West Bengal, India were analyzed by the procedure as described in section Procedure for Cr^{VI} and Cr^{III}. The results have been presented in Table 4. The results are in good agreement with a reference method²¹ (*t*-test, *P* = 0.05). Comparison of the present method with some other existing methods has been shown in Table 5²⁴⁻²⁶.

Conclusions :

Polymeric matrix containing *N*-(3-indolylmethyl) L-methionine moiety have been used for pH dependent selective removal and chemical speciation of inorganic chromium species from environmental samples. The functionalities present in the solid polymeric matrix contain carboxylate anion, tertiary nitrogen (from amino acid part) and another nitrogen donor present in indole moiety which are possibly responsible for binding to Cr^{III} at higher

Table 5. Comparison of the present method with some other existing methods

Matrix	LOD (mg mL ⁻¹)		Eluent	Pre-concentration factor		Sample analysed
	Cr ^{III}	Cr ^{VI}		Cr ^{III}	Cr ^{VI}	
Acetyl acetone modified XAD-16 ²⁴	0.02	0.014	2 mol L ⁻¹ HNO ₃ and 2 mol L ⁻¹ NaOH	100	140	Industrial samples
Cr ^{VI} -Dowex M 4195 chelating resin ²⁵	NA	1.94	4 mol L ⁻¹ NH ₃	NA	95	Natural and waste water samples
2-Naphthol-3,6-disulphonic acid ²⁶	NA	NA	4 mol L ⁻¹ HCl	97	97	Binary synthetic mixtures, natural water samples
Present method	0.4	1.3	3 and 4 mol L ⁻¹ HCl	220	246	Industrial samples, binary synthetic mixtures

NA = Not available.

Scheme 1. Sorption-desorption cycle of the resin.

pH. At low pH (acidic) nitrogen centers become protonated and act as an anion exchanger for Cr^{VI}. Total sorption-desorption cycle is presented in Scheme 1.

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